

Breadboard development of a Lunar Dust Analyzer. Y. Li¹, P. Fröhlich¹ and R. Srama¹, ¹University of Stuttgart (Pfaffenwaldring 29, 70569 Stuttgart).

Introduction: We describe the breadboard development of a lunar dust analyzer and preliminary calibration results. A dust sensor is designed for lunar surface exploration missions, including landers, rovers, and astronaut-led deployments, to perform characterization of three dust populations above the lunar surface: the dust particles naturally lofted by local electric field, the interplanetary particles (IDPs) and their impact ejecta particles, which cover wide mass, charge and velocity ranges. The designed lunar dust sensor has an open area of around 0.01 m². The dust acceleration facilities operated at the University of Stuttgart will be used to directly test and calibrate the dust sensor.

Lunar dust environment: The lunar dust is one of the highest-priority issues for a future human or robotic exploration. Lofted dust [1], IDPs and their impact ejecta grains [2] are three main components of the dust environment above the lunar surface with particle speeds ranging from m/s to 30 km/s.

Figure 1. Dust environment above the lunar surface.

Sensor design: A sketch of the lunar dust sensor is shown in Figure 2. It consists of one shield stage, two electrode arrays, one deflection stage, and one impact target. Each grid electrode is connected to an individual charge sensitive amplifier (CSA). Since the amplitude recorded by the traversed grid electrode is constant for various entry locations and incident angles, the particle's charge can be measured directly [3].

Figure 2. Sketch of the lunar dust sensor.

The particle's trajectory and entry location are calculated from the ratio of the signals on the traversed grid electrode and neighboring electrodes. The speed of the dust particle is determined from the particle's trajectory and the time of flight between the two grid electrode planes.

The high electric field in the deflection stage between two grid electrode arrays bends the particle trajectory [4]. For lofted particles, their charge-to-mass ratio can be calculated from particle trajectory differences before and after the deflection stage. Impact ionization signals recorded at the impact target are used to calculate particle mass for IDPs and their ejecta grains with speeds above 1 km/s.

Concept design of grid electrode plate: The electrode array is the key component in the lunar dust sensor, which performs the major measurement of particle charges, trajectories and speeds. The preliminary design of the electrode plates is shown in Figure 3. The four electrodes and their connected CSAs are integrated on one PCB.

Figure 3. Layout design of the electrode PCB.

Test facilities: Three different dust facilities are planned for the lunar dust sensor tests: (1) A vibration dust source with particle speeds ranging from 1 m/s to several m/s; (2) A 30 kV dust source and a LINAC dust accelerator facility with particle speeds from 10 m/s to 5 km/s; (3) A 2-MV dust accelerator facility with particle speeds from 1 km/s to 30 km/s.

References:

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- [2] Grün E. et al. (2011) *Planet. Space Sci.*, 59, 1672-1680.
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- [4] Wang X. (2024) *Planet. Sci. J.*, 5.